

COMPUTER SCIENCES

STEP-BY-STEP GREEDY ALGORITHMS WITH RESPECT TO WALSH SYSTEM

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Abstract

This paper proposes a modified step-by-step "greedy" algorithm for approximating functions with respect to Walsh system. This algorithm works iteratively, adding the next largest coefficient at each step and evaluating the approximation error. The paper describes the algorithm, its Python implementation, and examples of its application to test functions.

Keywords: greedy algorithm, Walsh system, Walsh-Fourier coefficients.

1. Introduction

The expansion of functions in systems of basis functions is a fundamental problem in various areas of mathematics and its applications. One widely used basis is the Walsh-Fourier system, based on Rademacher functions and their products. Efficient function expansions in the Walsh basis have important applications in signal processing, data compression, approximation theory, and other fields.

The classic method for constructing function approximations is the Fourier series truncation method, where the first N terms of the expansion are kept. However, this approach is not always optimal, as achieving good approximation accuracy may require a significant number of expansion terms. An alternative approach is the so-called "greedy" algorithms, which select the expansion terms not in the order of their appearance, but in the order of decreasing their weights (coefficients). This method often provides faster convergence for the same number of series terms.

This paper proposes a modified step-by-step "greedy" algorithm for approximating functions in the Walsh-Fourier system [1,2]. The classical "greedy" algorithm selects a fixed number n of the largest absolute Walsh-Fourier coefficients to approximate the function. However, this approach is not always optimal in terms of accuracy for a given number of series terms. The proposed algorithm works iteratively, adding the next largest coefficient at each step and evaluating the approximation error. The process stops once the error becomes less than a specified threshold ε . This allows achieving the required accuracy with a minimal number of series terms. The paper describes the algorithm, its Python implementation, and examples of its application to test functions. The results demonstrate that the modified "greedy" algorithm can provide more efficient approximations compared to the classical method and partial Fourier approximation when reaching the required level of accuracy.

2. Step-by-step "greedy" algorithm with respect to Walsh system

To define the Walsh function, it is necessary to define the Rademacher function [1].

Definition 1. The Rademacher system is defined as

$$r_0(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right), \\ -1, & x \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right], \end{cases}$$

$$r_0(x+1) = r_0(x), r_k(x) = r_0(2^k x), k = 1, 2, \dots,$$

i.e. to find the r_k Rademacher function, the interval $[0; 1)$ is split 2^{k+1} of equal subintervals, on each of which the $r_k(x)$ function takes $+1$ and -1 values successively.

The Walsh system is defined as all possible finite products of Rademacher functions. More precisely, we define the Walsh system by Paley numbering as follows [2,3]:

Definition 2. $W_0(x) \equiv 1$. Let n be any natural number, represented as $n = \sum_{s=1}^k 2^{m_s}$, $m_1 > m_2 > \dots > m_s$. The n -th Walsh function will be defined as follows:

$$W_n(x) = \prod_{s=1}^n r_{m_s}(x).$$

The function $f(x)$ is given. Let us denote its Fourier-Walsh n -th partial sum as follows:

$$S_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_k(f) W_k(x),$$

where $C_k(f) = \int_0^1 f(t) W_k(x) dx$ are the Fourier-Walsh coefficients of the function $f(x)$.

The greedy algorithms ([4]) with respect to Walsh system defined the following way.

Let's arrange the coefficients $\{C_k(f)\}$ in descending order of their absolute values, as follows:

$$|C_{\sigma(0)}(f)| > |C_{\sigma(1)}(f)| > \dots > |C_{\sigma(n)}(f)|$$

and consider the greedy approximant of the function $f(x)$. Let's designate it as follows:

$$G_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C_{\sigma(k)}(f) W_{\sigma(k)}(x):$$

It's known that the greedy algorithm, for example, for the Walsh system, is not always optimal ([5.6]).

In particular, we have shown that for example $f(x) = x^5$,

$$A = |f(x) - S_{50}(x)| = 0.0410837068979848,$$

and

$$B = |f(x) - G_{\delta}(x)| = 0.0530793301723754.$$

Thus, we find that $A < B$.

Now let's modify the algorithm by implementing a "greedy" approach with sequential steps. Our objective is to develop a "greedy" algorithm with incremental steps of arbitrary precision.

First, we fix an arbitrary number $\varepsilon > 0$. If $|f(x) - G_n(x)| < \varepsilon$, then the process halts, and the value of ε should be decreased.

We select from the sequence $\{C_k(f)W_k(f)\}$ the term $C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x)$ for which

$$|C_{\sigma(0)}(f)| = \max_{0 \leq k \leq n} |C_k(f)|,$$

and we estimate

$$|f(x) - C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x)|.$$

We verify the following condition:

$$|f(x) - C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x)| < \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

If the condition (1) is satisfied, then we compute the difference

$$|f(x) - G_n(x)| - |f(x) - C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x)|,$$

and the process halts.

If condition (1) is not met, then we define

$$f_1(x) = f(x) - C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x).$$

Now we select $C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)$ and create the difference

$$|f_1(x) - C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)|.$$

Let's reevaluate:

$$\begin{aligned} &|f_1(x) - C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)| \\ &= |f(x) \\ &\quad - C_{\sigma(0)}(f)W_{\sigma(0)}(x) \\ &\quad - C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)| \\ &< \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Again, if condition (2) is fulfilled, the process halts, and we calculate:

$$|f(x) - G_n(x)| - |f_1(x) - C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)|:$$

And if condition (2) does not occur, then we continue the process for the function:

$$f_2(x) = f_1(x) - C_{\sigma(1)}(f)W_{\sigma(1)}(x)$$

We continue this process until it stops at any step, meaning we will have

$$|f_k(x) - C_{\sigma(k)}(f)W_{\sigma(k)}(x)| < \varepsilon,$$

and then calculate the difference

$$|f(x) - G_n(x)| - |f_k(x) - C_{\sigma(k)}(f)W_{\sigma(k)}(x)|.$$

And if the process continues until reaching n , then we conclude that the outcome of the "greedy" algorithm with successive steps is equivalent to the outcome of the complete "greedy" algorithm.

The algorithm was implemented using a Python program. It takes inputs such as M (for the partial Fourier-Walsh sum calculation), n (for the complete "greedy" algorithm calculation), ε (precision level), and $f(x)$ (the function under consideration) data.

3. Code in Python

```
from scipy.linalg import hadamard
import sympy as sp
```

```
# Symbolic variable
```

```
x = sp.symbols('x')
```

```
M=int(input("Enter M number: "))
```

```
n = int(input("Enter n number for Greedy: "))
```

```
E=float(input("Enter epsilon: "))
```

```
# User input for the expression
```

```
user_input = input("Enter a mathematical expression in terms of 'x': ")
```

```
# Parse the user input into a SymPy expression
```

```
expr = sp.sympify(user_input) #function
```

```
def generate_x_values(M):
```

```
    return [k/M for k in range(M+1)]
```

```
x_values = generate_x_values(M)
```

```
#define Walsh
```

```
c_index=M # initial index
```

```
N = 1
```

```
N_check = 0
```

```
binary_length = 0
```

```
d_bool = False
```

```
while N_check < M:
```

```
    N = N * 2
```

```
    binary_length += 1
```

```
    if M > 0 and (M & (M - 1)) == 0:
```

```
        d_bool = True
```

```
        M += 1
```

```
    if M == 1:
```

```
        d_bool = False
```

```
    N_check = N
```

```
step_size = 1 / N
```

```
step_sizes = [i * step_size for i in range(N + 1)]
```

```
hadamard_matrix = [hm for hm in hadamard(N)]
```

```
def index_convert(N, l):
```

```
    walsh_index = []
```

```
    for i in range(N):
```

```
        decimal_number = i
```

```
        desired_length = 1
```

```
        binary_number = format(decimal_number,
```

```
                                f"0{desired_length}b")
```

```
        reversed_code = binary_number[::-1]
```

```
        walsh_index.append(int(reversed_code, 2))
```

```
    return walsh_index
```

```
walsh_index = index_convert(N, binary_length)
```

```
walsh_function = [hadamard_matrix[i] for i in walsh_index]
```

```
M=c_index
```

```
def calculate_coefficients(integrated_expr,
step_sizes, walsh_function, c_index):
```

```
    differences = []
```

```
    for interval_start, interval_end in
zip(step_sizes[:-1], step_sizes[1:]):
```

```
        integrated_value_start = inte-
```

```
grated_expr.subs(x, interval_start)
```

```
        integrated_value_end = inte-
```

```
grated_expr.subs(x, interval_end)
```

```

difference = float(integrated_value_end - integrated_value_start)
differences.append(difference)

coefficients = []
for c in range(c_index + 1):
    c_list = [diff * walsh for diff, walsh in zip(differences, walsh_function[c])]
    coefficient = sum(c_list)
    coefficients.append(coefficient)

return coefficients

integrated_expr = sp.integrate(expr, x)
coefficients = calculate_coefficients(integrated_expr, step_sizes, walsh_function, c_index)
sorted_c=sorted(coefficients,key=lambda x: abs(x), reverse=True)#decreasing order

def get_f_for_x(x_values, step_sizes, w):
    w_x = []
    for i, x in enumerate(x_values):
        for j in range(len(step_sizes) - 1):
            if step_sizes[j] <= x < step_sizes[j + 1]:
                w_x.append(w[j])
                break
        else:
            w_x.append(w[-1])
    return w_x

f_x=[]
for j in range(M+1):
    expr_value = expr.subs(x, x_values[j])
    f_x.append(expr_value)

def calculate_cw(coefficients, walsh_function, M, N):
    c_w = []
    for j in range(M+1):
        c_w_values = []
        for i in range(N):
            c_w_values.append(coefficients[j] * walsh_function[j][i])
        c_w.append(c_w_values)
    return c_w

c_w = calculate_cw(coefficients, walsh_function, M, N)
sorted_cw=calculate_cw(sorted_c,walsh_function,M,N)

c_w = []
walsh_values_in_x = []
sorted_c_w_in_x=[]
for i in range(M+1):
    w_x = get_f_for_x(x_values, step_sizes, walsh_function[i]) #Values of w_i(x)
    cw_x=get_f_for_x(x_values,step_sizes,sorted_cw[i])
    walsh_values_in_x.append(w_x)
    sorted_c_w_in_x.append(cw_x)
    transposed_sorted_cw_x = [[row[i] for row in sorted_c_w_in_x] for i in

```

```

range(len(sorted_c_w_in_x[0]))] # cw(0),...cw(1), cw(1)

sigma = []
s=[] #for fourier M
for row in transposed_sorted_cw_x:
    row_sum = sum(row[:n+1])
    sum_fourier=sum(row[:M+1])
    sigma.append(row_sum)
    s.append(sum_fourier)

#greedy normal
a=[]
for i in range (M+1):
    fs=abs(f_x[i]-sigma[i])
    a.append(fs)
B=sum(a)/len(a)

#Fourier
fourier=[]
for i in range (M+1):
    four=abs(f_x[i]-s[i])
    fourier.append(four)
A=sum(fourier)/len(fourier)

#greedy step by step
b=[]
b_without_abs=[]
f_k=[]
greedy_step=0
t=False
while t==False:
    while t==False:
        for i in range(n+1):
            for j in range(M+1):
                b_i_without_abs=f_x[j]-sorted_c_w_in_x[i][j]
                b_i=abs(f_x[j]-sorted_c_w_in_x[i][j])
                b.append(b_i)
                b_without_abs.append(b_i_without_abs)
            greedy_step+=1
            GS=sum(b)/len(b)
        if b_i<E:
            t=True
            break
    else:
        f_x=b_without_abs
        b=[]
        b_without_abs=[]
        t=False

break

print("Greedy Normal Form=",B)
print("Greedy step by step=",GS)
print("Fourier approximation=",A)
print("steps=",greedy_step)
The results of the algorithm are then presented in the following format:

```

Example 1.

$M = 50,$
 $n = 20,$
 $\varepsilon = 0.13,$
 $f(x) = x$

Greedy Normal Form= 0.0702512254901961

Greedy step by step= 0.0638235294117647

Fourier approximation= 0.0702512254901961

step=3, where 'step' indicates in which steps the algorithm performed the approximation with the accuracy ε .

Example 2.

$M = 80,$
 $n = 60,$
 $\varepsilon = 0.1,$
 $f(x) = x^8$

Greedy Normal Form= 0.0451854271375904

Greedy step by step= 0.0451854271375904

Fourier approximation= 0.0453110690028777

In this example, the values of Greedy Normal Form and Greedy step by step are identical, which means that the "greedy" algorithm with successive steps continued the calculations until completion, reaching n , and as a result matched the outcome of the full "greedy" algorithm.

Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed a modified step-by-step "greedy" algorithm for approximating functions in the

Walsh basis with arbitrary precision. The classical "greedy" algorithm fixes the number of expansion terms, which is not always optimal in terms of approximation accuracy. The proposed algorithm works iteratively, adding terms until the required accuracy is achieved. The Python implementation and examples demonstrate that this approach can provide more efficient approximations compared to classical methods when reaching a given accuracy level. Future work will investigate the convergence and error estimates for the modified algorithm.

References

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